

GAN-BASED PERSON REIDENTIFICATION USING DWT

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ABSTRACT

Person Re-identification (Re-id) is used in real-world applications for non-invasive biometric surveillance, validation, and identification of people in congested areas. In this paper, we propose GAN-based Person Reidentification using DWT. Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) generates identical persons with altered postures that appear in the output images. For every picture of a person, eight new photos are produced by defining a set of eight predefined poses. In order to extract features, the Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) technique is used which breaks down images into three high-frequency bands and one low-frequency band. The one low-frequency band of one-fourth of the size of the original image is considered for the final features with less noise. The features of test and database images are compared using Cityblock, Euclidean Distance (ED), and Cosine Similarity approaches. Through enhanced feature discrimination made possible by this dual technique, people are effectively re-identified from various camera angles and improve recognition accuracy by up to 99%.

Keywords: DWT, Deep learning, GAN, Matching features, Person Reidentification.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Person Re-identification (Re-ID) identifies a person across images or videos taken by different cameras. This involves detecting and tracking individuals and using features such as appearance, body shape, and clothing to match their identity in various frames. It is a complex task that often utilizes deep learning techniques. Pose Invariant Embedding (PIE) is used in deep person re-identification to address the challenges posed by pedestrian misalignment and pose variations [1]. It serves as a descriptor that aligns pedestrians to a standard pose, which enhances the robustness of person re-identification across different views and conditions.

This approach seeks to mitigate issues arising from detector errors and varying poses, ultimately improving identification accuracy. A more reliable identification model that functions across several datasets is required since the two scenarios merged in-person Re-ID seeks to identify individuals who have been photographed by numerous cameras at various times and locations. Various camera settings, lengthy gallery searches, low recognition rates, viewpoint, stance, illumination, and thick background changes are some of the challenges that Person Re-ID systems must overcome.

The primary method for person re-identification is appearance-based, demonstrating resilience to variations in posture, lighting, and vision, while emphasizing the representation of distinguishing characteristics [2, 3]. Other established techniques in metric learning or optimal subspace learning can be employed to identify the optimal metric for a specified set of features [4, 5, 6]. The feature representation employs similarity matching techniques to determine the shortest distance between probing photos and the complete gallery collection, facilitating the identification of an accurate match. Various measurement methods are utilized in this context, such as the Bhattacharyya distance [7], Mahalanobis distance [8], and Euclidean distance [9].

The GAN is an artificial intelligence model employed for unsupervised learning, consisting of two neural networks—a discriminator and a generator—developed concurrently through adversarial training, first described by Ian Goodfellow in 2014 [10]. The discriminator evaluates the new data instances for authenticity, whereas the generator creates new instances that resemble real data. The GAN is a highly versatile artificial intelligence tool, demonstrated by its numerous applications in image synthesis, style transfer, and text-to-image synthesis. GAN applications create images and movies, transfer styles, augment data, convert images to different images, generate realistic synthetic data for machine learning model training, and enhance image resolution.

Contribution: GAN-based person Re-Id utilizes GAN to produce eight additional pose images with every individual and features are extracted using DWT to enhance recognition accuracy, reaching up to 99%. The method incorporates DWT for feature extraction by decomposing images into one low-frequency and three high-frequency bands. This dual approach allows for improved feature discrimination, aiding in effective person re-identification across different camera views.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

It includes a thorough review of the body of knowledge regarding person reidentification. Research on deep learning models, feature extraction strategies, data augmentation approaches, and assessment metrics applied to person reidentification tasks are covered in this section. Xu et al., [11] proposed a solution to the issues of poor quality and limited quantity of data, thereby facilitating person reidentification (ReID). In picture annotations, incorrect labels are classified as dirty quality. In instances of insufficient quantity, specific identities possess a minimal number of photographs (Few IDs). Training with mislabelled data or a limited number of IDs using triplet loss will lead to low generalization performance. The Weighted Label Correction based on Cross-Entropy (WLCCE) technique was utilized to resolve the label error issue. The feature simulation based on the autoencoder (FSAE) approach is employed to generate virtual samples for Few ID, thereby addressing the issue of low quantity. An autoencoder (AE)-based simulator is trained to transfer various patterns of identities from multiple images (Mult IDs) to Few IDs, ensuring the validity of the simulated features.

Zhang et al., [12] suggested Dual-Graph Contrastive Learning (Dual-GCL) to make use of the interactions and relationships between the cases as well as the centroids produced by the clustering technique. To start, a dual graph is built using the feature space's affinities and the pseudo-label space that results from the clustering technique with node-to-node contrastive learning is carried out. The dual graph and the centroids' relationships are captured by dual-GCL at both the node and super-node levels. By using two layers of contrastive learning, it is possible to align the centroids between various cameras in the same embedding space and encode multilayer structural representations between the instances that correspond to the nodes in a dual graph. Utilizing the semantic link, a camera-aware augmentation approach reduces the disparity in the domain between cameras. Tan et al., [13] suggested a two-module Multi-level Feature Aggregated Transformer (MFAT) for person re-identification. (i) The module for global multi-level information aggregation called Global Content and Structure Aggregation (GCSA). (ii) To aggregate multi-level features using local operations, the Local Convolution Aggregation (LCA) module is made up of a number of convolutional blocks. Fan et al., [14] presented the use of features from several transformer layers to create a skip connection aggregation transformer (SCAT) network that would enhance feature diversity and align visible body parts in obscured images. Among the varied features are the following: First, there are intermediate layer features that prioritize alignment by focusing on pedestrians in nonoccluded areas; second, there are high layer features that concentrate on global information; and third, there are fine-grained local features that are derived from part pooling encoder and fusion reconstruction module. It is suggested to use the fusion reconstruction module and the part pooling encoder to produce fused local features and part-based local features, respectively. Lv et al., [15] proposed a technique that uses a graph-convolutional network to integrate the connections between bones and joints in humans into a high-level representation for re-identification. In this, an edge score predictor module uses biological data from the human skeleton to depict the interactions between human joints and bones, which are then encoded into a learnt adjacency matrix.

Si et al., [16] suggested a homogeneous and heterogeneous optimization with modality style adaption (HHO) mechanism for unsupervised VI-ReID that removes intermodality and intramodality disparities without label knowledge. In addition to increasing visual diversity and bridging the intermodality gap, the modality style adaption technique transfers unlabeled cross-modality pedestrian styles. To extract intramodality pedestrian features, homogeneous feature optimization is developed. To further decrease the discrepancy in intermodality, heterogeneous feature optimization is employed. Mining trustworthy cross-modality signals for every identity is done via a heterogeneous feature search (HFS) module. Different identities are compelled to be kept apart when these trustworthy heterogeneous features are limited to produce the compact feature distribution. Zhang et al., [17] developed an ARA (adaptive relation attention) network for person re-id that is based on the ARA mechanism and successfully handles the problems associated with person re-id. A relation branch and an adaptation branch make up the ARA module. Through the mining of relationships between feature nodes, the relation branch obtains the global structural information. For attention features produced by the relation branch, the adaptation branch creates dynamic weights. They created the Internet of Behavior (IoB), which integrates the Internet of Things with artificial intelligence and plays a key role in developing a smart city that can acquire the behavior status of pedestrians at different times and places. Zhu et al., [18] Examined how implicit 3-D body shape representations could be used as pixel-level guidance to enhance the extraction of identification traits beyond appearance by include body shape knowledge. Body form as supervision, instead of input, allows for consistent integration with pixel-wise appearance features and shape-aware enhancements without increasing computing costs. Additionally, pixel-level features align across frames with form awareness enabling video-based person reidentification, guaranteeing temporal consistency.

Gao et al., [19] developed an identity-guided collaborative learning scheme (IGCL) for individuals changing clothes Re-ID involves collaborative learning that is directed by the constancy of identity and effectively utilizes human semantics. In scenarios where clothing attention and mid-level collaborative learning are employed, a degradation stream for clothing attention is established to effectively reduce the interference from clothing information. The human semantic attention mechanism and a body jigsaw stream replicate various representations of the same identity, while prioritizing human semantic information. The extraction features are suitable for variations in pedestrian behavior while also focusing on human semantic information that is contextually irrelevant. A comprehensive unified framework is employed to concurrently analyze all streams, with optimization directed by the identity. Zhang et al., [20] provided a part-based nondirect coupling embedded GAN technique that limits the characteristics of various blocks by incorporating a similarity measure loss. It seeks to identify more characteristics that a person in various postures has in common. Because of this, the network's extracted features are resilient to changes in an individual's posture, and the test stage doesn't need any new pose data or processing overhead. Ku et al., [21] offered a technique to increase the accuracy of human re-identification that relies on manually chosen feature fusion and convolutional neural networks (CNNs). First, the Inception structure is used to extract features from the input photos. Second, to modify the Inception network's learning process and create fusion features—which are utilized in a softmax classifier—a manually chosen feature module is introduced.

Liu et al., [22] introduced a method that combines convolutional neural networks and the Siamese architecture to solve the top-down reidentification challenge. Here, a single Siamese network that has been trained to predict the similarity or distance between two input images can distinguish between a pair of top-down images. Experiments have demonstrated that, once suitably trained, the model can learn new classes of individuals in real-time, enabling one-shot, top-down re-identification. Teng-Yok Lee [23] demonstrated a visualization-based method for comprehending a Person ReID algorithm running on CNN. Given two photos, they created a method to estimate the amount that each element in a CNN layer contributes to the similarity between their feature vectors since Person ReID algorithms are frequently built to map images of the same person into comparable feature vectors. Using the estimate as a guide, they develop a visualization tool that, instead of painstakingly going over every element, allows users to interactively find and see when certain elements are activated. The visualization tool explores a Person ReID data set, finds challenging examples, and examines the rationale behind their similarities using a variety of user interaction widgets. Lei Qi et al., [24] Proposed Adversarial Camera Alignment Network (ACAN) to enhance individual re-identification. Images from many cameras were integrated into a unified subspace by Multi-Camera Adversarial Learning (MCAL) for camera alignment. Two methodologies are examined for addressing the multi-camera confrontational task: the established gradient reversal layer (GRL) framework and the planned structure of other Camera Equiprobability (OCE).

De Cheng et al., [25] Developed a human re-identification technique utilizing optimal fusion algorithms, enhancing the robust combination strategy to attain superior re-ranked matching results by factoring in recognition capabilities. The ranking results derived from the test datasets are utilized in the study. Minxian Li et al., [26] Introduced Unsupervised Tracklet Association Learning (UTAL), a deep learning methodology for unsupervised re-identification. To optimize the identification of trackless distinctiveness for matching both within and across camera views, it is utilized to extract the primary re-identifying information from the person-tracked data in an end-to-end manner and to learn the intra-camera tracking list. Navaneet K L et al., [27] suggested a union function that operates on query and gallery match deep feature illustrations. To improve the representation of inquiries, a specific optimization technique is used.

Jianjun Lei et al., [28] introduced the effective metric learning technique known as mapping space topology constraint (MSTC) and a robust example known as Semantic Region Representation (SRR). By examining the many bodily parts, the SRR uses semantic representations to achieve an operational correspondence between the consistent regions, emphasizing the focal point in opposition to the background intrusion. The MSTC considers the topological relationships among each sample within the feature space. Long Wei et al., [29] A method known as Self-Inspired Feature Learning (SIF) has been proposed to enhance the performance of Re-Identification networks through optimization techniques. The network is assisted in learning more about discriminatory person descriptions through a basic confrontational learning approach. With this method, the network's structure is preserved throughout the testing phase while an auxiliary branch is introduced during the training phase. Wenfeng Song et al., [30] suggested a Context-Interactive CNN (CI-CNN) that uses multi-task Reinforcement Learning (MTRL) to identify the temporal and spatial surroundings. Through the use of actor-critic methods, the CI-CNN restructures multitask reinforcement learning to obtain both spatial and temporal information simultaneously.

Mang Ye and Pong C. Yuen [31] Introduced a purifyNet to enhance neural networks and equitably refine the interpreted labels by incrementally modifying the expected labels. This model enhances a hard-aware instance re-weighting strategy by simultaneously reducing unneeded noise labels and concentrating on complex samples with accurate labels. Hong-Xing Yu et al., [32] proposed a cross-view clustering approach utilizing an unsupervised asymmetric distance measure. The asymmetric distance metric facilitates accurate feature conversions for each camera view to rectify feature misrepresentations. To improve view-specific preferences and optimize potential cross-view discriminative data for unsupervised re-identification, the Deep Clustering-based Asymmetric Metric Learning (DECAMEL) acquires a dense cross-view cluster configuration of re-identification data.

3. PROJECTED MODEL

The proposed approach consists of two primary components, as shown in Fig 1: a GAN used to generate images of a person with different angles and a person re-id feature extraction model to identify a person with the help of DWT compressed and less noise technique.

Fig. 1 Block Diagram of the proposed methodology

3.1 BENCHMARKED IMAGE DATASETS OF PERSONS:

The two standard image datasets such as Market-1501 and CUHK01 are used to test the performance of the projected method:

3.1.1 Market-1501 [33]

The dataset serves as a comprehensive public benchmark specifically developed for person re-identification tasks. The data set was gathered in front of a supermarket at Tsinghua University. Six cameras are utilized, comprising five high-resolution cameras and one low-resolution camera. There are two parts to the dataset: one part is used for training with 750 identities, while the other part is used for testing with 751 identities.

Fig 2. The dataset images of Market-1501 [33]

The attributes are labeled at the identity level, resulting in a file with 27×751 attributes for training and 27×750 attributes for testing. The 27 attributes include gender, hair length, sleeve length, lower-body clothing length, type of lower-body clothing, hat-wearing status, backpack carrying, bag carrying, handbag carrying, age, eight colors of upper-body clothing, and nine colors of lower-body clothing. Each person typically has 3.6 photos per perspective, and 32,668 pedestrian image bounding boxes were obtained using the Deformable Part Models pedestrian detector. The example photographs are shown in Fig 2.

3.1.2. CUHK01 [34]: Each subject has at least two photographs from two distinct camera angles, 3,884 individually cropped shots, and 971 themes as shown in the picture examples in Fig 3. A range of camera positions and angles are used in the database; camera *B* mostly records frontal and back-end views, while camera *A* takes probing photos.

Fig 3. Sample images from the CUHK01 dataset [34]

3.2. POSE-REGULARIZATION GAN MODEL

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think and learn like humans [35, 36]. The systems are intended to carry out operations like reasoning, problem-solving, comprehending natural language, identifying patterns, and decision-making that normally demand for human intellect. AI technologies are implemented using various methods, including Machine Learning (ML) where systems learn from data, Deep Learning (DL) which is a subset of ML that uses neural networks to model complex patterns, and natural language processing, which enables machines to understand and generate human language [37, 48]. The chief difference between DL and ML is the use of simple neural networks with one or two computational layers in ML, however, DL models use three or more layers typically hundreds or thousands of layers to train the models. The DL is a technology that can help solve almost any type of science or engineering problem.

Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) is a DL technology, which is a subset of ML that focuses on using deep neural networks to automatically learn and extract features from large datasets. While ML encompasses a broader range of algorithms, including supervised and unsupervised learning techniques, DL specifically involves advanced neural network architectures, which require substantial amounts of data to perform optimally. GAN consists of two Convolutional Neural Networks—the generator and the discriminator—that use deep learning methods to compete against each other, enabling them to learn and generate new data. The GAN is a generative model, they create new data that resemble the training data. GANs are primarily categorized as unsupervised learning algorithms. However, they can incorporate supervised methods within their framework for certain applications. The GANs have various applications in real-world scenarios such as advertising, Science, Video games, Audio synthesis, photorealistic images, reconstructing 3D models of objects from images and model motion patterns in video, developing age face photographs that determine individuals' faces according to their age, denoise in images, data augmentation, reconstruct individual faces after listening to their voice, generate text, articles, songs, poems, etc [39].

The purpose of the image generator is to produce pictures of the same subject in several positions. The input image of a person and the target position image are combined to create a new human image with eight distinct postures. The image generator is made up of two modules: a Generator and a Discriminator, just as all other GAN models. It is possible to teach the generator to change a person's appearance, but it is position-specific. By distinguishing between created and actual data samples, the discriminator improves the quality of the generated image.

3.2.1 Pose normalization

Pose-normalized image generation for person re-identification uses generative adversarial networks (GANs) to synthesize realistic person images based on specific poses, improving the effectiveness of recognizing individuals despite changes in orientation or appearance. This approach allows for better matching of individuals across different camera views by normalizing their poses in the generated images. The Pose-Normalized Generative Adversarial Network (PN-GAN) [40], is a deep learning model designed for synthesizing realistic images of persons based on specific poses. It addresses challenges in-person image generation and re-identification by normalizing images to a common pose, enabling better generalization and performance in tasks such as person re-identification. It focuses on synthesizing realistic images of individuals based on specific poses. This technology is particularly useful in applications requiring identity verification from various viewpoints.

Realtime multi-person 2D pose estimation using part affinity fields is a technique developed to detect the poses of multiple individuals in images by identifying body, foot, hand, and facial key points. This method utilizes a nonparametric representation to efficiently analyze the spatial relationships between different body parts, allowing for accurate and quick pose detection in real-time applications [41]. As can be seen in Fig 4, the model, which is centered on the concept of pose regularization, is comprised of only eight pre-established postures that have a variety of pose angles.

Fig 4. Eight poses on Market-1501[40]

The GAN model is comprised of two main components: a generator and a discriminator, as illustrated in Fig 5. An input image and a target image of the same individual in a different pose are utilized to produce a new image reflecting the target pose.

Fig 5. GAN model

3.2.2 Generator of GAN

The generator employs an encoder-decoder architecture, wherein the encoder initially transforms the input image of the individual into eigenvectors. The decoder utilizes its internal representations and learning weights to reconstruct the data. Fig 6 illustrates the encoder-decoder architecture utilized for the generator.

Fig 6 Generator Structure

The target pose image and the RGB original image are both 128 x 64 pixels in size. They are concatenated to create a 256 x 128 image. The resulting images are supplied into the generator's encoder as input images. The eigenvectors are obtained by using a Deep Convolution Network (DCN). Table 1 and Table 2 contain tabulations of the encoder and decoder structures, respectively. To improve normalization using batch norm 16, the kernel size is being increased from 3 to 7.

Table 1 Structure of the Encoder

Layers	Input		Kernel Size	Stride	Padding	Output	
	Size	Channel				Size	Channel
1	256X128	3	7	1	0	250X122	64
2	250X122	64	3	2	1	125X61	128
3	125X61	128	3	2	1	63X31	256

Table 2 Structure of the Decoder

Layers	Input		Kernel Size	Stride	Padding	Output	
	Size	Channel				Size	Channel
1	63X31	256	3	2	1	125X61	128
2	125X61	128	3	2	1	250X122	64
3	250X122	64	7	1	0	256X128	3

3.2.3. Discriminator

Through binary classification, the discriminator seeks to distinguish between produced and genuine images. The objective of optimization is to identify the optimal generator G_P . The initial phase involves the iterative minimization of the generator loss function $L_{(G_P)}$ and the discriminator loss function $L_{(D_P)}$ until convergence is achieved. The discriminator's encoder consists of 2D Convolution and Leaky ReLU. Fig 7 depicts the architecture of the Discriminator, and Table 3 lists the corresponding structural values.

Fig 7. Discriminator Structure

Table 3 The Structure of Discriminator

Layers	Input		Kernel Size	Stride	Padding	Output	
	Size	Channel				Size	Channel
1	256X128	3	4	2	1	128X64	64
2	128X64	64	4	2	1	64X32	128
3	64X32	128	4	2	1	32X16	256
4	32X16	256	4	2	1	16X8	512
5	16X8	512	4	2	1	8X4	512
6	8X4	512	4	1	1	7X3	512
7	7X3	512	1	1	0	7X3	512
Adaptive AvgPool2d	7X3	512	--	--	--	1	512

3.3. FEATURE EXTRACTION BY DWT

This tool effectively converts spatial domain images into the frequency domain, comprising low and high-frequency coefficients, utilizing low and high-pass filters with a decimation factor of 2. The Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) is utilized on an image's window to extract low- and high-frequency coefficient bands. The frequency domain comprises four bands of equal size, which include three high-frequency bands and one low-frequency band. The fundamental information of the original facial image resides in the low-frequency band. The minor edge data of the original face image is present in three high-frequency bands corresponding to horizontal, vertical, and diagonal edges. Our method focuses on low-frequency band coefficients while excluding high-frequency band coefficients as features for face recognition, yielding low-dimensional final features that facilitate high-speed computation [42, 43]. The coefficients for the low-frequency band Low-Low (LL) and the high-frequency bands Low-High (LH), High-Low (HL), and High-High (HH) are obtained using equations 1-5 for an image matrix of size 2×2 .

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} \text{-----(1)}$$

$$LL = \frac{a+b+c+d}{2} \text{-----(2)}$$

$$LH = \frac{a+b-c-d}{2} \text{-----(3)}$$

$$HL = \frac{a-b+c-d}{2} \text{-----(4)}$$

$$HH = \frac{a-b-c+d}{2} \text{-----(5)}$$

Where a, b, c, and d are the coefficients of the 2X2 matrix.

The DWT is applied to the images produced by the GAN to acquire the corresponding resultant four DWT bands of LL, LH, HL, and HH coefficients. In conclusion, the LL band matrix is the sole factor that is taken into account for subsequent processing. This matrix is composed of compressed, significant, and noiseless information. There are numerous wavelet varieties, such as Haar, Daubechies, Biorthogonal, Coiflets, Symlets, Morlet, Mexican Hat, Meyer, Beta wavelet, Hermitian wavelet, and Spline wavelet. Each wavelet possesses distinctive characteristics that render it appropriate for a variety of signal processing and analysis applications [44, 45].

3.4. MATCHING

3.4.1 City block distance: The total of the absolute differences between two places' coordinates on a grid is known as the Manhattan distance [46]. The distance between two points, a and b, in k dimensions is determined using equation (6).

$$CB = \sum_{j=1}^k |a_j - b_j| \text{-----(6)}$$

3.4.2 Euclidean Distance:

The square root of the total of the squared differences between the two vectors is used to determine the straight-line distance between two pixels [47] as given by equation (7),

$$ED(p,q) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=2}^n (q_i - p_i)^2} \text{-----(7)}$$

Where p and q are the two points in Euclidean n-space

q_i, p_i is the Euclidean vectors, starting from the origin of the space (initial point) and n is n-space.

3.4.3. Cosine Distance:

Cosine distance quantifies the difference between two vectors, while cosine similarity quantifies their resemblance [48] given in Equations (8) and (9).

$$\text{Cosine distance} = 1 - \text{Cosine similarity} \text{-----(8)}$$

$$\text{Cosine similarity} = \text{Cos}(\theta) \text{-----(9)}$$

Where θ is the angle between 2 vectors

Cosine distance ranges from 0 to 2, where 0 indicates identical vectors, 1 indicates no association, and 2 indicates complete differences.

Examples of Cosine Similarity and difference

Consider 2 documents, A and B, represented by 2 vectors.

(i) The angle between 2 vectors A and B is 10°

Cosine similarity = $\text{Cos}(10) = 0.9848$, this represents two vectors A and B, which are 98.48% similarity.

Cosine distance = $1 - \text{cosine similarity} = 1 - 0.9848 = 0.0152$, representing two vectors A and B, which are 1.52% different.

(ii) Document Similarity and difference

Document Vector A: [1, 1, 1, 1, 1, 0]

Document Vector B: [1, 1, 1, 1, 0, 1]

The Cosine Similarity between 2 vectors A and B is given in Equation (10)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Cosine Similarity} &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i B_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n A_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n B_i^2}} \text{-----(10)} \\ &= \frac{1.1 + 1.1 + 1.1 + 1.1 + 1.0 + 0.1}{[\sqrt{1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2 + 0^2}] [\sqrt{1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2 + 1^2 + 0^2 + 1^2}]} \\ \text{Cosine Similarity} &= \frac{4}{[2.2360679775] [2.2360679775]} = 0.80 \end{aligned}$$

The two documents are similar by 80%

Cosine distance = $1 - \text{cosine similarity} = 1 - 0.80 = 0.20$

The two documents are different by 20%

4. RESULT ANALYSIS

4.1. Performance metric Rank-k:

The matching accuracy metric evaluates the likelihood that the top k retrieved results contain the correct match. The feature vector, x_p , derived from an unseen probe image is classified using established methods to ascertain its prototype label, c. The distance x_g of a gallery/target image's feature vector is calculated using the specified equation (11).

$$\text{Dist}(x^p, x^q) = \|(w^c)^T |x^p - x^q|\|_1 \text{----- (11)}$$

The matching ranks of x_p against a gallery of images can be obtained by sorting the distances computed from Equation 11, a smaller distance results in a higher rank.

4.2. DETAILS OF IMPLEMENTATION

Experiments using two benchmark datasets with different training sizes after feature extraction are used to evaluate the robustness and effectiveness of the suggested model. From each person's image samples, two equal-sized groups are chosen at random and assigned to training and testing. The goal of person reidentification is to use the learned model to find the image in the gallery set that corresponds to a test image. The first camera's image sequences are the probe set, while the second camera's image sequences are the gallery set. The likelihood of the two goals being the same rises as they converge. By calculating the distance between each image in the gallery set and a specific image in the probe set, a rank list may be produced. When the image that most closely matches the probe image is placed first in the rank list, signifying the accurate match, this is the ideal situation. Finding every target of interest at rank 1 is difficult and frequently leads to poor matching accuracy.

4.3. DISCUSSIONS OF THE RESULTS

4.3.1 Results on Market 1501 Dataset

The Market 1501 dataset, which includes pose variations, random occlusions, and apparel similarities, is used to compute the results. With 750 image pairs from the dataset, the suggested framework's performance is computed. The findings provide the assessment of the suggested framework for three distance matching strategies with rankings 1, 5, and 10 as shown in Table 1. The results with GAN-generated images are better than the images used directly from the dataset for all three matching distances. The matching technique Cosine similarity gives better results compared to cityblock and Euclidian Distance techniques. The results show that Cosine similarity using GAN-generated images has the greatest rank 1 matching rate of 97.87%.

Table 1. Ranked Matching Rates (%) on the Market 1501 dataset

Dataset	Matching Distance	% Rank 1	% Rank 5	% Rank 10
GAN Dataset	Cityblock	88.64	91.90	98.00
	Euclidean Distance	96.50	98.01	99.10
	Cosine Similarity	97.89	98.65	99.80
Original Dataset	Cityblock	85.30	89.90	95.80
	Euclidean Distance	92.66	94.39	97.77
	Cosine Similarity	93.40	96.79	98.01

4.3.2 Results on CUHK02 dataset

The results are calculated using the CUHK02 dataset with variations in pose, random occlusions, and clothing similarities. The performance of the proposed framework with 200 image pairs of the dataset is calculated. The results depict the evaluation of the proposed framework with ranks 1, 5, and 10 as presented in Table 2 for three distance matching techniques. The results with GAN-generated images are better than the images used directly from the dataset for all three matching distances. The matching technique Euclidian Distance gives better results compared to cityblock and Cosine similarity techniques. According to the results, the highest rank 1 matching rate of 88.90% is attained for Euclidian Distance with GAN-generated images.

Table 2. Ranked Matching Rates (%) on the CUHK02 dataset

Dataset	Matching Distance	% Rank 1	% Rank 5	% Rank 10
GAN Dataset	Cityblock	63.33	67.50	70.90
	Euclidean Distance	88.90	89.10	92.00
	Cosine Similarity	65.90	73.00	79.34
Original Dataset	Cityblock	62.81	65.20	69.21
	Euclidean Distance	80.23	82.90	89.29
	Cosine Similarity	63.56	74.90	80.24

4.3.3. Comparisons between the proposed method and the existing approaches

Table 3 displays the efficiency of the suggested model with three matching strategies compared to the current methods on the Market 1501 and CUHK01 datasets for the rank 1 matching rate.

Table 3. Comparison of the projected work and the existing methods

Authors	Techniques	% Rank 1	
		Market 1501	CUHK01
Kunhong Yu et al., [49]	GAN with LBRO algorithm + CNN baseline	78.33	--
Shuang Liu et al., [50]	Semantic Constraint GAN	93.30	58.20
Wu Lin et al., [51]	Hybrid deep architecture, LDA+PCA	-----	67.12
Wei Li et al., [52]	Harmonious Attention CNN	93.8	44.40
Proposed model with Cityblock	GAN +DWT	88.64	63.33
Proposed model with Cosine Similarity	GAN +DWT	97.89	65.90
Proposed model with ED	GAN +DWT	96.50	88.90

5. CONCLUSION

The ability to identify a person using several camera views for a variety of real-world security, area monitoring, and smart surveillance applications makes Person Re-Identification (Re-ID) a crucial task in surveillance data processing. The GAN-based Person Reidentification using DWT is presented in this paper. The same person with the different postures that show up in the output photographs is created using GAN. Eight unique pictures are created for each person's picture by defining a set of eight preset poses. The DWT approach, which divides images into three high-frequency bands and one low-frequency band, is used to extract features. For the final features with reduced noise, a single low-frequency band that is one-fourth the size of the original image is taken into consideration. Cityblock, Euclidean Distance (ED), and Cosine Similarity techniques are used to compare the attributes of test and database photos. The combined methodologies of GAN and DWT are used to improve recognition accuracy and successfully re-identify the individuals from several cameras.

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